

SYMMETRIZED (p,h) -CONVEXITY AND SOME HERMITE-HADAMARD-TYPE INEQUALITIES

Le Ba Thong¹

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SUMMARY

This paper introduces symmetrized (p,h) -convex functions and establishes some Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for the new class of functions.

Keywords: *symmetrized (p,h) -convexity, (p,h) -convexity, p -convexity, h -convexity, harmonically convexity, Hermite-Hadamard inequality.*

1. INTRODUCTION

A function f is said to be *convex* on a real interval I if

$f(\lambda x + (1-\lambda)y) \leq \lambda f(x) + (1-\lambda)f(y)$, for all $x, y \in I$ and $\lambda \in [0,1]$. An estimate of the (integral) mean value of a continuous convex function is known as Hermite-Hadamard inequality (Hadamard, 1893, Hermite, 1883). Precisely, if f is a convex function on a real interval I and $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$ then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x)dx \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}.$$

This inequality is one of the most useful inequalities in mathematical analysis. For new proofs, noteworthy extensions, generalizations, and numerous applications of this inequality, see e.g., (Dragomir & Pearce, 2003, Mitrinović & Lacković, 1985).

In recent years, convexity has been generalized and extended in various aspects using new and different concepts. These researches led to the appearance of several Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities. Among these generalizations, two interesting concepts are p -convex functions (Zhang & Wan, 2007) and h -convex functions (Varošanec, 2007). They are defined as follows:

Definition 1.1 (Zhang & Wan, 2007). Let $I \subset (0, \infty)$ be an interval and $p \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. We say that $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a p -convex function if

$$f([\alpha x^p + (1-\alpha)y^p]^{1/p}) \leq \alpha f(x) + (1-\alpha)f(y),$$

for all $x, y \in I$ and $\alpha \in [0,1]$.

Definition 1.2 (Varošanec, 2007). Let I, J be two real intervals with $J \supseteq (0,1)$ and let $h : J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a non-negative and non-zero function. We say that $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a h -convex function if f is non-negative and

$$f(\alpha x + (1-\alpha)y) \leq h(\alpha)f(x) + h(1-\alpha)f(y),$$

for all $x, y \in I$ and $\alpha \in (0,1)$.

These functions are continuously generalized to (p,h) -convex functions by Fang & Shi (2014):

Definition 1.3 (Fang & Shi, 2014). Let $I \subset (0, \infty)$ and $J \supseteq (0,1)$ be two real intervals, $p \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, and let $h : J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a non-negative and non-zero function. We say that $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a (p,h) -convex function if f is non-negative and

$$f([\alpha x^p + (1-\alpha)y^p]^{1/p}) \leq h(\alpha)f(x) + h(1-\alpha)f(y),$$

for all $x, y \in I$ and $\alpha \in (0,1)$.

In (Fang & Shi, 2014), the authors also derived Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for the class of (p,h) -convex functions as follows:

$$\frac{1}{2h(1/2)} f\left[\left[\frac{a+b}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right] \leq \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b x^{p-1} f(x)dx \leq (f(a) + f(b)) \int_0^1 h(t)dt. \quad (1.1)$$

In particular, if $p = -1$, (p,h) -convex functions become harmonically h -convex functions which are studied firstly by Noor & et al. (2015).

A significant generalization of h -convex functions is symmetrized h -convex functions, which are introduced by Dragomir (2016). To give this concept, the authors considered a symmetrical transform $\bar{f}$ of f on $[a,b]$ which is defined by

$$\bar{f}(x) := \frac{1}{2}[f(x) + f(a+b-x)].$$

Then we say $f : [a,b] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is symmetrized h -convex function on $[a,b]$ if $\bar{f}$ is h -convex on $[a,b]$. Moreover, if h integrable on $[0,1]$ and f integrable on $[a,b]$, Hermite-Hadamard-type inequality for symmetrized h -convex function is given as follows (Dragomir, 2016):

$$\frac{1}{2h(1/2)} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x)dx \leq [f(a) + f(b)] \int_0^1 h(x)dx. \quad (1.2)$$

¹Faculty of Natural Science and Technology, Tay Nguyen University;

Corresponding author: Le Ba Thong; Tel: 0978165041; Email: lbthong@ttn.edu.vn

Subsequently, by considering an other symmetrical transform $\tilde{f}$ of f on $[a, b]$ which is defined by

$$\tilde{f}(x) := \frac{1}{2} \left[f(x) + f\left(\frac{abx}{(a+b)x - ab}\right) \right],$$

Wu & et al. (2017) gave symmetrized harmonic convex functions. In addition, the authors also introduced symmetrized harmonic h -convex functions, which is the generalization of harmonically convex functions and h -convex functions. Furthermore, if h integrable on $[0, 1]$ and f is symmetrized harmonic h -convex and integrable on $[a, b]$, then Hermite-Hadamard-type inequality for f is given as follows (Wu & et al., 2017):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) &\leq \frac{ab}{b-a} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x^2} dx \\ &\leq [f(a) + f(b)] \int_0^1 h(x) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

Recently, İşcan (2020) used the p -symmetrical transform $P_{(f;p)}(x)$ of f on $[a, b]$ which is defined by

$$P_{(f;p)}(x) := \frac{1}{2} \left[f(x) + f\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) \right]$$

to define symmetrized p -convex functions, then they provided the following Hermite-Hadamard-type inequality for f which is symmetrized p -convex and integrable on $[a, b]$:

$$\begin{aligned} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) &\leq \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &\leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Essentially, the symmetrized h -convexity can be formed as symmetrized (p, h) -convexity, where $p = 1$, while the symmetrized harmonic h -convexity are in the case $p = -1$. The main purpose of this paper is study symmetrized (p, h) -convexity for the more general case, i.e. $p \neq 0$. After introducing the definition, we establish Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for the new class. Moreover, this class is a generalization from the previous versions so some results in (Dragomir, 2016, Wu & et al., 2017, İşcan, 2020) are special cases of our results.

2. RESEARCH CONTENTS & METHODS

2.1. Research contents

We introduce the concept of the symmetrized (p, h) -convex function.

We establish some Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities symmetrized (p, h) -convex functions.

2.2. Research method

Based on the theory of symmetrized (p, h) -convexity, we give the comparison to achieve the results.

We combine analytical techniques and comparative methods to derive properties and inequalities.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we consider a, b are positive numbers, $p \neq 0$, J is real interval satisfies $J \supseteq (0, 1)$ and the function $h: J \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is not identical to 0.

For a function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we recall that a p -symmetrical transform of f on the interval $[a, b]$ is denoted by $P_{(f;p)}$ and is defined by

$$P_{(f;p)}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[f(x) + f\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) \right],$$

for all $x \in [a, b]$.

Remark 3.1. If f is (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, then $P_{(f;p)}$ is also (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$. Indeed, it is easy to see that $P_{(f;p)}$ is non-negative and for all $x, y \in [a, b], \alpha \in (0, 1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &P_{(f;p)}\left([tx^p + (1-t)y^p]^{1/p}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[f\left([tx^p + (1-t)y^p]^{1/p}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + f\left([a^p + b^p - tx^p - (1-t)y^p]^{1/p}\right) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[f\left([tx^p + (1-t)y^p]^{1/p}\right) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. f\left([t(a^p + b^p - x^p) + (1-t)(a^p + b^p - y^p)]^{1/p}\right) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} h(\alpha) \left[f(x) + f\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) \right] + \\ &\quad \frac{1}{2} h(1-\alpha) \left[f(y) + f\left([a^p + b^p - y^p]^{1/p}\right) \right] \\ &= h(\alpha) P_{(f;p)}(x) + h(1-\alpha) P_{(f;p)}(y). \end{aligned}$$

However, if $P_{(f;p)}$ is (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ for a function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, then the function f is not necessarily (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$. For example, let $h(\alpha) = \alpha$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $p = -1$, consider $f(x) = -\ln x, x \in (0, 1)$. The function f is not (p, h) -convex but $P_{(f;-1)}$ is (p, h) -convex (Wu. & et al. 2017).

Definition 3.2. A function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ if the p -symmetrical transform $P_{(f;p)}$ is (p, h)

-convex on $[a, b]$.

In other words, a function f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ if

$$\begin{aligned} & P_{(f;p)}\left([\alpha x^p + (1-\alpha)y^p]^{1/p}\right) \\ & \leq h(\alpha)P_{(f;p)}(x) + h(1-\alpha)P_{(f;p)}(y), \end{aligned}$$

for all $x, y \in [a, b]$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

By Remark 3.1, if f is (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, then f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$. Also, if $[c, d] \subset [a, b]$ and f symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, this does not imply in general that f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[c, d]$.

Example 3.3. Let $J \supseteq (0, 1)$, and the function $h: J \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ satisfies $h(\alpha) \geq \alpha$, for all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, and $\lambda \geq 2$. Then the function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f(x) = (x^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1}$, $p > 0$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$.

Indeed, for any $u, v \in [a, b]$ and any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, by convexity of the function $g(\psi) = \psi^{\lambda-1}$, $\psi \geq 0$, it is easily seen that

$$\begin{aligned} & f\left([\alpha u^p + (1-\alpha)v^p]^{1/p}\right) \\ & = (\alpha u^p + (1-\alpha)v^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1} \\ & = (\alpha(u^p - a^p) + (1-\alpha)(v^p - a^p))^{\lambda-1} \\ & \leq \alpha(u^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1} + (1-\alpha)(v^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1} \\ & \leq h(\alpha)(u^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1} + h(1-\alpha)(v^p - a^p)^{\lambda-1} \\ & = h(\alpha)f(u) + h(1-\alpha)f(v). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $P_{(f;p)}$ is also (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$. Therefore f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$.

Proposition 3.4. Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g(x) = x^{1/p}$, $x > 0$, $p \neq 0$. A function f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ if and only if $f \circ g$ is symmetrized h -convex on $g^{-1}([a, b]) = [a^p, b^p]$ (or $[b^p, a^p]$).

Proof. Let f is a symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ and $x, y \in g^{-1}([a, b])$ be arbitrary, then there exists $u, v \in [a, b]$ such that $x = u^p$, $y = v^p$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \overline{f \circ g}(\alpha x + (1-\alpha)y) \\ & = \frac{1}{2} \left[(f \circ g)(\alpha x + (1-\alpha)y) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (f \circ g)(a^p + b^p - \alpha x - (1-\alpha)y) \right] \\ & = \frac{1}{2} \left[f([\alpha u^p + (1-\alpha)v^p]^{1/p}) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + f([a^p + b^p - \alpha u^p - (1-\alpha)v^p]^{1/p}) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$= P_{(f;p)}\left([\alpha u^p + (1-\alpha)v^p]^{1/p}\right).$$

Since f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, it is easily seen that

$$\begin{aligned} & P_{(f;p)}\left([\alpha u^p + (1-\alpha)v^p]^{1/p}\right) \\ & \leq h(\alpha)P_{(f;p)}(u) + h(1-\alpha)P_{(f;p)}(v) \\ & = \frac{1}{2} h(\alpha) \left[f(u) + f([a^p + b^p - u^p]^{1/p}) \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{2} h(1-\alpha) \left[f(v) + f([a^p + b^p - v^p]^{1/p}) \right] \\ & = \frac{1}{2} h(\alpha) \left[(f \circ g)(x) + (f \circ g)(a^p + b^p - x) \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{2} h(1-\alpha) \left[(f \circ g)(y) + (f \circ g)(a^p + b^p - y) \right] \\ & = h(t)\overline{(f \circ g)}(x) + h(1-t)\overline{(f \circ g)}(y). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $f \circ g$ is symmetrized h -convex on $g^{-1}([a, b])$.

Conversely, if $f \circ g$ is symmetrized h -convex on $g^{-1}([a, b])$ then it is easily seen that f is symmetrized (p, h) -convex by a similar procedure. The details are omitted. $\square$

Theorem 3.5. Assume that $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex and integrable on $[a, b]$ with h is integrable on $[0, 1]$. Then we have the Hermite-Hadamard-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \leq \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ & \leq [f(a) + f(b)] \int_0^1 h(x) dx. \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Proof. Since $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, then by writing the Hermite-Hadamard-type inequality (1.1) for the function $P_{(f;p)}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \leq \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{P_{(f;p)}(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ & \leq [P_{(f;p)}(a) + P_{(f;p)}(b)] \int_0^1 h(x) dx. \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

It is easily seen that

$$P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) = f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right),$$

$$P_{(f;p)}(a) + P_{(f;p)}(b) = f(a) + f(b),$$

and

$$\frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{P_{(f;p)}(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx = \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx.$$

Then by (3.2), required inequality are got.

Remark 3.6. In Theorem 3.5, if it is chosen $p=1$ then the inequality (3.1) reduce to the inequality (1.2). If it is chosen $p=-1$ then the inequality (3.1) reduce to the inequality (1.3).

Remark 3.7. By helping Proposition 3.4, the proof of Theorem 3.5 can also be given as follows:

Since $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on the interval $[a, b]$, $f \circ g$ is symmetrized h -convex on the interval $g^{-1}([a, b]) = [a^p, b^p]$ (or $[b^p, a^p]$) with $g(x) = x^{1/p}, x > 0, p \neq 0$. So by inequality (1.2), it is obtained that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}(f \circ g)\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) &\leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b (f \circ g)(x) dx \\ &\leq [(f \circ g)(a) + (f \circ g)(b)] \int_0^1 h(x) dt, \\ &\text{i.e.} \\ \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) &\leq \frac{p}{b^p - a^p} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &\leq [f(a) + f(b)] \int_0^1 h(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.8. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, then for any $x \in [a, b]$, we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) &\leq P_{(f;p)}(x) \\ &\leq \left[h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) + h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \right] \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since $P_{(f;p)}$ is (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$ then for any $x \in [a, b]$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) &\leq h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \left[P_{(f;p)}(x) + P_{(f;p)}\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

and since

$$\begin{aligned} P_{(f;p)}(x) + P_{(f;p)}\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) &= f(x) + f\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right) = 2P_{(f;p)}(x) \end{aligned}$$

while

$$P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) = f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right),$$

we get the first inequality in (3.3).

Also, by the (p, h) -convexity of $P_{(f;p)}$ we have for any $x \in [a, b]$ that

$$\begin{aligned} P_{(f;p)}(x) &= P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[b^p \frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p} + a^p \frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p} \right]^{1/p}\right) \\ &\leq h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) P_{(f;p)}(b) + h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) P_{(f;p)}(a) \\ &= \left[h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) + h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \right] \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

which gives the second part of (3.3).

Remark 3.9. In Theorem 3.8, if we choose $p=1$, then the inequality (3.3) reduce to the inequality (3.18) in Theorem 7 in (Dragomir, 2016). If we choose $p=-1$ then the inequality (3.3) reduce to the inequality (4.3) in Theorem 6 in (Wu & et al., 2017) and if it is chosen $h(\alpha) = \alpha, \alpha \in (0, 1)$, then the inequality (3.3) reduce to the inequality (18) in Theorem 2.2 in (İşcan, 2020).

Remark 3.10. By helping Proposition 3.4 and Theorem 7 in (Dragomir, 2016), the proof of Theorem 3.8 can also be given. The details are omitted.

Corollary 3.11. Assume that the function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetrized (p, h) -convex and integrable on $[a, b]$ with h is integrable on $[0, 1]$. If $w : [a, b] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is integrable on $[a, b]$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \int_a^b \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx &\leq \int_a^b \frac{w(x) P_{(f;p)}(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &\leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \int_a^b \left[h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) + h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \right] \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx. \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

Moreover, if w is p -symmetric with respect to $\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}$ on $[a, b]$, i.e.

$w(x) = w\left([a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}\right)$, for all $x \in [a, b]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} f\left(\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \int_a^b \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx &\leq \int_a^b \frac{w(x) f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &\leq [f(a) + f(b)] \int_a^b h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

Proof. The inequality (3.4) follow by (3.3)

multiplying by $w(x)/x^{1-p} \geq 0$ and integrating over x on $[a, b]$.

By changing variables and using the fact that w is p -symmetric with respect to $\left[\frac{a^p + b^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}$, we

have

$$\int_a^b \frac{w(x) f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right)}{x^{1-p}} dx = \int_a^b \frac{w\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right) f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx = \int_a^b \frac{w(x) f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &= \int_a^b h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \frac{w\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right)}{x^{1-p}} dx. \\ &= \int_a^b h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b \frac{w(x) P_{(f;p)}(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_a^b \frac{w(x) f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx + \int_a^b \frac{w(x) f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right)}{x^{1-p}} dx \right] \\ &= \int_a^b \frac{w(x) f(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \quad (3.6) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \int_a^b \left[h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) + h\left(\frac{b^p - x^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \right] \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx \\ &= [f(a) + f(b)] \int_a^b h\left(\frac{x^p - a^p}{b^p - a^p}\right) \frac{w(x)}{x^{1-p}} dx. \quad (3.7) \end{aligned}$$

By (3.6), (3.7), and (3.4), the inequality (3.5) are got.

Remark 3.12. If it is chosen as $p = 1$, then the results in Corollary 3.11 reduce to the results in Corollary 2 in (Dragomir, 2016) and if it is chosen $p = -1$ then the inequality (3.4) reduce to the inequality (4.4) in Corollary 1 in (Wu & et al., 2017).

Remark 3.13. By helping Proposition 3.4 and Corollary 2 in (Dragomir, 2016), the proof of Theorem 3.11 can also be given. The details are omitted.

Theorem 3.14. Assume that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

is symmetrized (p, h) -convex and integrable on $[a, b]$ with h is integrable on $[0, 1]$. Then for any $x, y \in [a, b]$, we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \left[f\left(\left[\frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - \frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \right] \\ & \leq \frac{p}{y^p - x^p} \left[\int_x^y \frac{f(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt + \int_{[a^p + b^p - y^p]^{1/p}}^{[a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}} \frac{f(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt \right] \\ & \leq \left[f(x) + f(y) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - y^p\right]^{1/p}\right) \right] \int_0^1 h(t) dt. \quad (3.8) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since $P_{(f;p)}$ is (p, h) -convex on $[a, b]$, then $P_{(f;p)}$ is also (p, h) -convex on any sub-interval $[x, y]$ (or $[y, x]$), where $x, y \in [a, b]$.

By writing Hermite-Hadamard (1.1) for $P_{(f;p)}$ on $[x, y]$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \leq \frac{p}{y^p - x^p} \int_x^y \frac{P_{(f;p)}(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt \\ & \leq \left[P_{(f;p)}(a) + P_{(f;p)}(b) \right] \int_0^1 h(t) dt. \quad (3.9) \end{aligned}$$

By the definition of $P_{(f;p)}$, it is easily seen that

$$\begin{aligned} & P_{(f;p)}\left(\left[\frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[f\left(\left[\frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - \frac{x^p + y^p}{2}\right]^{1/p}\right) \right], \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_x^y \frac{P_{(f;p)}(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_x^y \frac{f(t) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - t^p\right]^{1/p}\right)}{t^{1-p}} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_x^y \frac{f(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt + \frac{1}{2} \int_x^y \frac{f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - t^p\right]^{1/p}\right)}{t^{1-p}} dt \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_x^y \frac{f(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt + \frac{1}{2} \int_{[a^p + b^p - y^p]^{1/p}}^{[a^p + b^p - x^p]^{1/p}} \frac{f(t)}{t^{1-p}} dt$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & P_{(f;p)}(x) + P_{(f;p)}(y) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[f(x) + f(y) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - x^p\right]^{1/p}\right) + f\left(\left[a^p + b^p - y^p\right]^{1/p}\right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By (3.9), we deduce the desired result (3.8).

Remark 3.15. If we choose $p = 1$, then (3.8) reduces inequality (3.14) in Theorem 6 in (Dragomir, 2016) and if it is chosen $p = -1$ then the inequality (3.8) reduce to the inequality (4.1) in Theorem 5 in (Wu & et al., 2017).

Remark 3.16. By helping Proposition 3.4 and Theorem 6 in (Dragomir, 2016), the proof of Theorem 3.14 can also be given. The details are omitted.

4. CONCLUSION

The paper established some Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for symmetrized (p, h) -convex functions which is a generalization of symmetrized harmonic h -convex functions, symmetrized p -convex functions, and symmetrized h -convex functions. We can see that those results are extensions of the results in the previous research.

TÍNH (p, h) -LÒI ĐỐI XỨNG HÓA VÀ MỘT SỐ BẤT ĐẲNG THỨC KIỂU HERMITE-HADAMARD

Lê Bá Thông¹

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TÓM TẮT

Bài báo này giới thiệu hàm (p, h) -lồi đối xứng hóa và thiết lập một số bất đẳng thức kiểu Hermite-Hadamard cho lớp hàm mới.

Từ khóa: (p, h) -lồi đối xứng hóa, (p, h) -lồi, p -lồi, h -lồi, lồi điều hòa, bất đẳng thức Hermite-Hadamard.

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¹Khoa Khoa học Tự nhiên và Công nghệ, Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên;
Tác giả liên hệ: Lê Bá Thông; ĐT: 0978165041; Email: lbthong@ttn.edu.vn.